

**Meaning of time and space slip coefficients k_t and k_s -
Formula for calculating spatial values**

People might wonder, if $k_t = k_s/c^2$, what are the values of k_t and k_s ? Actually, this is a ratio used to convert time to space. We can assume $k_t = 1$.

As mentioned in the previous article, time is essentially space. Specifically, when we measure time, we are measuring the variation in the total value of space throughout the universe. People use days, months, years, hours, minutes, and seconds as units of measurement instead of the units used for space.

Therefore, from the slip coefficients, we can completely convert time to space. For example, from the age of the universe calculated in years (since humanity uses years as the unit of measurement for time), we can change the unit of time measurement to the unit of space measurement and then multiply by the corresponding slip coefficient to calculate the value of space created.

Let's return to the formula for calculating the time dilation of two reference frames, one stationary (time t) and one moving (time t').

t^2 is the change in the total spatial value of the entire universe in the stationary frame.

$(t')^2$ is the change in the total spatial value of the entire universe in the moving frame.

Thus, the difference $t^2 - (t')^2$ is the spatial value created by the moving frame for the stationary frame.

From this, we have the formula: $Sv = t^2 - (t')^2 = s^2 / c^2 (k_t = 1)$

Applying S_v to explain Minkowski's formula:

Minkowski's formula: $S^2 = c^2t^2 - s^2$

$$\Leftrightarrow S^2/c^2 = t^2 - s^2/c^2 = t^2 - S_v = (t')^2$$

From this, we can explain why S^2 remains unchanged when we change the stationary reference frames, because S^2/c^2 is $(t')^2$, which is the change in the total spatial value of the entire universe of the moving system. Stationary systems can change t and s due to the choice of time to calculate the change in spatial value, but this does not affect the change in the total spatial value of the entire universe of the moving system. This is also the meaning and nature of S^2 in Minkowski's formula.

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.